

GENERAL NOTIONS OF PHRASEOLOGISMS AND THEIR HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation. *This article deals with the problems of phraseology in Modern linguistics. It gives information about general notions of phraseological units and its historical development.*

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In linguistics, the history of the development of the science of phraseology can be divided into three periods:

1. Includes the period from the middle of the 18th century to the 30s of the 20th century. This period is the start of phraseological research. In the first period, the scientific activity of mature linguists M.V. Lomonosov, V.I. Dal, A.A. Potebnya, F.F. Fortunatov, F.I. Buslayev, Charles Bally, A.A. Shakhmatov developed and served as a foundation in the formation of the field. At that time, phraseology, lexicography, that is, served as an object of practical lexicology, and mainly the reflection of phraseological units in dictionaries, their meaning, and etymology were given special importance.

2. The 30-50s of the 20th century is the second period in the development of phraseology. This period can also be called the period of formation of phraseology as an independent linguistic field. During this period, advanced linguists such as Y.D. Polivanov, V.V. Vinogradov, S.I. Abakumov, G.K. Danilov, G.O. Vinokur, A.I. Yefimov worked effectively in the field of phraseology and created a number of scientific works, monographs, and textbooks. During this period, many candidate and doctoral theses were devoted to the study of phraseology.

3. From the 60s of the 20th century until now, it is the third period of the field of phraseology. This period is associated with the development of phraseological theories and the use of methods in phraseological research. During this period, a lot of researches took place, and phraseology gained its place and position in linguistics as a separate field. Prof. Y.A. Malinovsky created a monograph entitled "The Formation of Russian Phraseological Theory in the 20th Century". In the monograph, the scientist

divides the history of the formation of phraseology in the 20th century into 4 periods:

1) Phraseological doctrine that emerged in Russian linguistics at the beginning of the 20th century (1900-1920s);

2) Development of phraseology in Russian linguistics in the period before the Great Patriotic War (1920-1940s);

3) the development of phraseology in Russian linguistics in the 1950s and 1960s;

4) The development of phraseology in Russian linguistics in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century.

5) The services of V.V. Vinogradov in the development of the field of phraseology as a separate science [1;19] are significant. In his scientific works, he divides phraseologisms into three classes:

1. Phraseological fusions.

2. Phraseological compounds.

3. Phraseological collocations.

The meanings of the components of the first group of phraseologisms are units that are not related to the meanings of their whole units. For example: heavy father - the main role in the play; to kick the bucket - to die; Phraseologisms such as red tape - bureaucratic method are phraseologisms that have the same meaning as a whole.

Phraseological confusion is a combination of words whose meaning has completely changed. However, unlike phraseological compounds, their meaning cannot be understood from the meanings of their components. Phraseological compounds are phraseologisms whose meaning is understood from the phraseological meaning of a whole phraseology. The transfer of meaning based on metaphor is clear and obvious. Lexical

components of phraseological compounds are the most stable expressions.

For instance: to look a gift horse in the mouth (to eramine a person critically; to find fault with smth one gained without effort); to ride the high horse (to behave in a superior, haughtily, overbearing way); a big bug (a person to importance); to fish out of water (a person situated uncomfortably outside his usual or proper environment).

Since the phraseological material is complex and multi-faceted, in recent years it has been studied using various methods and methods. At this point, it is necessary to highlight the following methods and methods of studying phraseological units: Identification method. It is worth mentioning the prominent linguists Charles Balli and A.V. Kunin as its major representatives. Contextual method. Its representative is N.N. Amosova, who mainly studied the phraseological units included in the text.

Also, the variational method (V.L. Arkhangelsky), the phraseological application method (V.P. Zhukov), the structural-typological method (L.I. Raizenzon, Y.K. Avaliani, Y.P. Solodub), the comparative method (S.G. Gavrin), the method of learning phrases based on semantic circles (M.G. Tashev), the method of learning lexemes and phrases into denotative and connotative terms (M.M. Kopilenko) [3;12]. The above-mentioned methods complement each other and allow a deeper understanding of different types of phraseological units, paradigmatic and syntagmatic features, valence possibilities [1;13].

Phraseological units are close to lexical units according to the plan of content, and according to the plan of expression they are close to syntactic units (phrases, sentences). But phraseological units are not equivalent to a word, a phrase, or a sentence. Studying the issues of phraseology, researching this field led to its formation as an independent linguistic field. He enriched the science of linguistics theoretically and practically. However, it should not be concluded that there are no unexplored problems in the field of phraseology.

The term phraseologism also served to express different meanings in Turkic studies. Mirza Kozimbek, a Turkic scholar who lived in

the 19th century, based on the traditions of that time, used the word "phrase" in his work in the sense of "sentence", "speech", as in other descriptive grammars written in Russian [1; 37]. When it is called a phraseological combination, it means large language units. Azerbaijani linguists B. Choponzoda and F. Oghazoda discussed the branches of language science in their work "Turkish Language Grammar", and together with the terms "Semasiology", "Stylistics" were widely used in linguistics at that time. used the word "idiotism" against the term "idiomatism".

Phraseology is one of the relatively young fields in Turkic studies, because its systematic study, the study of the semantic-grammatical functional features of phraseological units began in the 40-50s of the 20th century. Taking into account that phraseological units are functionally close to words, some linguists considered them lexical word combinations or lexical units and included them in the scope of the object of study of the fields of syntax or composition.

As in Russian linguistics, the scope of phraseology in the narrow and broad sense continues to be understood in Turkic studies as well. Phraseologisms in a broad sense include all fixed combinations (proverbs, proverbs, idiomatic units, their non-idiomatic fixed phraseological groups and pairs of words). Their unifying common feature is stability and ready presence in language [2; 36]. S.K. Kensbojev singled out the groups that are the direct basis for understanding phraseology in a narrow sense.

In linguistics, there is an opinion that "the object of phraseology is a stable set of words used as a separate language unit." When this idea was put forward, scientific works were published that revealed the essence of the concept of "stable compound" in the language.

Phraseological units differ from static compounds. These differences are as follows:

- a) semantic integrity;
- b) imagery;
- c) figurative meaning.

Conducting comparative-typological researches in the field of phraseology opens a wide way to solving general theoretical problems of phraseology. In general, it has a much broader content than the etymological analysis of the sources of formation of phraseological

combinations. This is a general philological problem, and determining the stages of formation of the oldest, first philological models is considered an important semiotic problem [3; 76].

The study of phraseological combinations related to the names of various things, events and places, and the names of people is considered one of the current issues in modern linguistics. Linguist D. Niyazmetova in her article "Linguistic study of phraseology with a food component in English" (Biblical materials) states that the study of phraseology in linguocultural science is one of the topical and controversial issues [2; 71]. It is possible to observe the use of linguistic analysis and statistical methods in determining the semantic, linguo-cultural characteristics of phraseology with a food component related to the Bible, in the analysis of dictionaries.

Words and phrases from the holy religious book are widely presented in the book "Studies in English, Written and Spoken" by S.Stoffen. In the chapter "Scriptural phrases and Allusions in Modern", the scientist studies and scientifically analyzes biblical phrases and their etymology. In Western linguistics, the study of biblicalisms is again associated with the name of L.P. Smith. In his book "Phraseology of the English Language", he devoted a separate section to biblical phrases and studied them. The author writes that "the number of biblical idioms and phrases in the English language is so large that it is not an easy task to collect and list them" [4; 65]. L.P. Smith notes that the English language contains not only many biblical words, but also biblical idiomatic expressions that represent the literal translation of ancient Hebrew and Greek idioms. As a result of the analysis, the following are examples of phraseological combinations with a food component related to the Bible:

- **Adam' apple** – qo'shtomoq, kekirdak olmasi;

- **The apple of Sodom** – chiroyli, ammo aynigan ho'l meva;

- **Milk and honey** – to'kin-sochinlik, mo'l-ko'llik;

- **Manna from heaven** – zor-intizor bo'lib kutmoq;

- **A forbidden fruit** – ta'qiqlangan ho'l meva [5; 46].

Biblical phraseological phrases in English with a food component include food names such as "apple", "bread", "milk", "fat", "olive". There are also phraseological units related to place names in English. Their analysis and research can be found in the scientific work of M. Rajabova [6; 70]. The study of place names is considered not only as an object of linguistics, but also of history and geography. Linguistic and cultural research of the phraseologisms with place names, highlighting their national and cultural aspects is one of the urgent issues of modern linguistics. The following units can be cited as an example of phraseologisms related to place names: have kissed the Blarney stone. In Ireland, there is a big stone in front of Blarney Castle, and according to the legends of the English people, a person who kisses this stone will have the vice of flattery and flattery; go for a Burton - to die, turn a blind eye, disappear without a trace. Barton is a small brewing town in Staffordshire. This phrase was first used by British pilots during World War II to remember their comrades-in-arms who died in the war.

Most of the national and cultural phraseological units are related to the people's daily lifestyle, customs and traditions. Most of them arise in national-cultural conditions and enrich the phraseological layer of the language. Thus, the issue of the research of phraseological units in linguistics was mainly formed in the 50s of the 20th century in our country, while phraseology gained a strong place among several branches of linguistics by the 70s and 80s. Many scientific works have been created in this field, and various textbooks and training manuals have been written, and the number of phraseological scientists has expanded.

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